

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Full paper

STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

All papers published in this conference proceedings have been peer reviewed through a peer review process administered by the proceedings Editors. Reviews were conducted by expert referees to the professional and scientific standards expected of a conference proceedings.

Proceeding Editors

Nicolas Robinson-Garcia
Daniel Torres-Salinas
Wenceslao Arroyo-Machado

Citation: Vandewalle, E., Guns, R., & Engels, T. C. E. (2022). Exploring the use of lib citations as an altmetric with local public libraries. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti22147). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6975659>

Copyright: © 2022 the authors, © 2022 Faculty of Communication and Documentation, University of Granada, Spain. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#).

Collection: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sti2022grx/>

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Exploring the use of lib citations as an altmetric with local public libraries¹

Eline Vandewalle*, Raf Guns* and Tim C.E. Engels*

*Eline.Vandewalle@uantwerpen.be, raf.guns@uantwerpen.be, tim.engels@uantwerpen.be
ECOOM, University of Antwerp, Middelheimlaan 2, Antwerp, 2020 (Belgium)

Introduction

Lib citations or Library Catalog Analyses are a bibliometric indicator based on the number of *library holdings* or *catalog inclusions* of books. They were introduced more than ten years ago by White et al. (2009) and by Torres-Salinas and Moed (2009) as a new indicator for measuring the impact of books. The lib citation score is a type of *altmetric* in the sense that it is an alternative to the traditional metrics based on citations. However, whereas most altmetrics are based on internet sources (mentions on twitter, views on Mendeley etc.) (Priem, Taraborelli, Groth, & Neylon, 2010), the lib citation score is based on the physical presence of books in libraries. In a very basic sense, they are meant to reflect the cumulative judgement of librarians about what could be of interest to their audience. Even though lib citations were conceived from the beginning as indicators of ‘cultural impact’ (White et al., 2009), evidencing the broader appeal of books, they have primarily been based on catalogues of research libraries. In this study, we take a different approach, focussing on the availability of books in local public libraries as an indicator of broad cultural appeal in a local context; we will call this indicator the *public lib citation*.

We argue that the choice of library is important. As the audiences of public libraries and research libraries are different, library holding counts in public libraries cannot have the same interpretation as those in research-oriented libraries. Zuccala and White (2015) made a distinction between members of the Association of Research Libraries and non-members. So far, most lib citation studies have relied on OCLC’s WorldCat as it is the most comprehensive catalogue of books (Halevi, Nicolas, & Bar-Ilan, 2016; Linmans, 2010; Maleki, 2021; Sieber & Gradmann, 2011; Torres-Salinas, Arroyo-Machado, & Thelwall, 2021; White & Zuccala, 2018; Zuccala & Guns, 2013; Zuccala & White, 2015). However, the OCLC has been found to have an English language (Anglo-Saxon) bias (Linmans, 2010). Since we are interested in books that are mostly written in a national language, it makes sense to turn toward a comprehensive national catalogue.

This choice is meant to highlight the local dissemination of books, as well as the dissemination of books to a wider audience. In this paper, we discuss just what this “wider

¹ This work was funded by the Flemish Government through its support to ECOOM, as part of the program on the study of interdisciplinarity and impact.

dissemination to the broader public” looks like by looking at the properties of SSH books that can be found in local public libraries.

Data

Our dataset is based on all 46 641 ISBNs (of books, chapters and proceedings) that were submitted to the Flemish database for Social Sciences and Humanities (VABB-SHW) between 2000 and 2019. The VABB-SHW was created in the context of the Flemish performance-based research funding system (PRFS) and holds records of publications by researchers affiliated with a Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) department at a Flemish institution. Flanders is a semi-autonomous region within the country Belgium. The data is submitted on a yearly basis by the Flemish universities. A panel of senior scholars, the GP, decides which publications adhere to all inclusion criteria.

These ISBNs were used for querying the Cultuurconnect catalog, which holds the records of Flemish public libraries. This also includes the Dutch-speaking part of Belgium’s bilingual capital Brussels. As a result, our dataset contains a comprehensive overview of the availability of SSH books in the Flemish public libraries. In total, the number of libraries present in our dataset is 639. The number of ISBNs that were associated with a record in Cultuurconnect was 9302. Not all of these, however, were also being held in the libraries (sometimes records were made but the books not actually acquired, or books were removed from the libraries). The number of ISBN’s with a holding is 8675 or approximately 18.6% of the total dataset. For reference, this percentage is much lower than for the presence in local research libraries, where it lies over 50%.

Upon initial data exploration, it was found that the main library of the city of Hasselt holds an unusually large amount of books written by SSH scholars. The reason for this is that it also holds the collection of a university college. We therefore opted to exclude this library from a large part of the analysis – knowing, however, that this also excludes the books that would have been part of their public library collection. The resulting number of ISBNs used in the analysis is 7543 (16.2%).

Our dataset is not limited to books authored by Flemish SSH researchers, contributions can be authorship of a monograph, author of a chapter or book editor. This can result, for example, in a critical edition of a literary work becoming part of our dataset. We opted to keep these books in the dataset because they also belong to the output of SSH scholars and more particularly with their broader engagement with topics of wide appeal. The dataset is limited to books written by SSH scholars in Flanders and their presence in Flemish public libraries. The availability of international SSH research or the spread of local SSH research internationally is therefore beyond the scope of this study.

Maleki (2021) has argued that in libcitation analyses, a distinction needs to be made between library print holdings and library e-holdings. In our dataset but very few books could be identified as not in print, these were mostly books for listening and easy reading. We therefore opted not to make the distinction.

Methods

For books that had records in the Flemish public libraries, it was possible to aggregate the records on work-level because the cataloguing system makes use of identifiers based on the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) framework (Riva et al., 2017) to group records. The implementation of the FRBR theory in the Flemish library cataloguing

system is described in a document on the Open Vlacc website called (*FRBR in Open Vlacc: Theorie en invoerafspraken*, 2021). We based our grouping of works on their use of identifiers assigned to “works”.

Firstly, we added a simple binary variable, representing whether or not the book appeared at least once in the public libraries. This variable is especially important since most of the scores amount to zero or very low values. The binary score was used to create a subset of books that appeared at least once in the public libraries. Secondly, we calculated the number of items or holdings for each of the books found in public libraries, to create a *public libcitation score*. This holding count represents the number of items available in the libraries. In the case of books with multiple volumes, the volumes were all counted as one item, even though it is possible for users to lend the individual volumes.

Results

The public libcitation score

Excluding the library of Hasselt, only about 16.2% of books have a public libcitation score larger than 0, meaning that most books written by Flemish SSH scholars do not appear in local public libraries. Figure 1 shows that these scores are skewed with many outliers.

Figure 1. Simple holding counts – data distribution

Properties of SSH books that appear in public libraries

We now turn towards some of the properties of SSH books that are held in local public libraries. A comparison between the languages used most frequently in books from the entire VABB-SHW database and books present in public libraries, shows that English is the dominant language in for all books in VABB-SHW, but Dutch – the language spoken in Flanders – is the most frequent language among the books in public libraries. French and German – the other two national languages of Belgium- represent smaller numbers of books in our dataset.

Figure 2. Comparison of main languages in public libraries compared with the whole database

Secondly, we make a distinction between scholarly and non-scholarly books, based on their status in the Flemish PRFS. A distinction is made between books that count towards the PRFS ('VABB-approved') and books that do not count ('rest'). Figure 3 shows that the 'rest' category contains the majority of books, both for books submitted to the VABB-SHW and for the subset of books found in the public libraries. However, for the category of books in public libraries, this category is even greater.

Figure 3. Comparison of VABB-SHW books (by ISBN) and books in public libraries by category

The difference between the average public libcitation scores of scholarly and non-scholarly books shows that non-scholarly SSH books are more present in local public libraries. The average public libcitation scores of non-scholarly books is 4,4, compared with only 0,5 for the scholarly books.

Discussion

As mentioned, we draw our attention to a particular type of libcitation: the libcitation in local public libraries. There has been extensive literature about public libraries as a unique institution embodying democratic ideals by being open to all and providing access to education, opportunities for lifelong learning, and a free space for citizens to be (Aabø, 2005; Barclay, 2017). The ideal of universal information is tied primarily to the accessibility of information, while the provision of a physical space ties libraries firmly to their local context. Public libraries service local communities. Even though the digital age has pressured public libraries to rethink their role, the institution of the public library has remained important. In a study of American public libraries, Barclay (2017) has reported a rise in both visits to public

libraries and items borrowed from public libraries per capita in the first decade of the 21st century.

Nevertheless, the advent of the internet has reduced the role of libraries for reference purposes. The same study of Barclay (2017) found a significant drop in reference questions. Moreover, digitized publications are becoming ever more important, including digitized book publications. However, an argument can be made that while researchers and academics have no qualms using online publications and books in pdf form rather than physical copies of books when conducting research, the physical presence of books can still be seen as an important indicator of availability for local public libraries. An analysis of the use of e-books in academic and public libraries in Sweden has shown that e-book acquisitions are on the increase in both public and academic libraries and that the increase in e-book lending could offset the decline in lending of print books (Macevičiūtė & Borg, 2013).

The general trends in public libcitation scores show that the SSH books held in local public libraries are typically not peer-reviewed and fall outside the scope of the PRFS, which is directed towards the funding of scholarly peer-reviewed literature. This means that the public libcitation score can be especially useful for the study of non-scholarly literature. In the framework of Hicks (2005), non-scholarly literature is one of the four types of literatures of the social sciences.

The books that appear in public libraries are also more likely to be written in Dutch. Both aspects of the books that appear in public libraries – not being of a scholarly nature and being written in a local language – show that the public libcitation score captures a different element from other indicators, not scholarly impact, but the distribution and availability of books to a broader audience.

Conclusion

This short paper has drawn attention to a new source for libcitation analyses: libcitations from local public libraries. We have used a catalogue of local public libraries to calculate public libcitation scores for all books written by Flemish SSH scholars. An exploratory analysis of SSH books with a presence in local libraries has shown that non-scholarly SSH books are more likely to appear in local public libraries. It also shows that the books written by SSH scholars that appear in local public libraries are more likely to be written in Dutch. Rather than being indicators of scholarly impact, public libcitations are a tool that can be used specifically to gauge the impact of books that are not peer-reviewed and that are written in a local language.

This study has shown that it is possible to perform libcitation studies with local public libraries. However, a few drawbacks have to be noted. Firstly, the analysis depends on a cataloguing system specific to the country or region under study rather than an international catalogue where all data can be retrieved in one go. Cross-country comparisons would have to take into account the differences between the public library catalogues and on a broader level also depend on the availability of data about local public libraries. The results with regard to libcitation scores have also shown that while the number of books written by local SSH scholars and present in public libraries is not negligible, it is also not very great. Thus, the public libcitation score can only be used for a limited number of books.

Lastly, it is important to stress a few limitations of this study. Some important issues with libcitation analyses (that also apply to public libcitations) were raised by Biagetti (2017) and

Biagetti, Iacono and Trombone (2018). The libcitation scores as ‘citation scores by librarians’ suggests that librarians decide on the acquisition of individual books. In practice, however, books are often bought in bulk. Donations can also play a role. A second major issue is the prevalence of online books. As books become more and more available – and read – online, the interpretation of the libcitation score becomes more complex. The current study did not take into account the library acquisition policy. This could help in gaining an understanding into the extent to which bulk buying may influence the result, but also which books are seen as relevant to librarians. In future research, we will investigate these issues, in order to better assess the potential and limitations of (public) libcitation scores as an indicator of broader impact.

References

- Aabø, S. (2005). The role and value of public libraries in the age of digital technologies. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 37(4), 205–211.
- Barclay, D. A. (2017). Space and the Social Worth of Public Libraries. *Public Library Quarterly*, 36(4), 267–273.
- Biagetti, M. T. (2017). Effectiveness and limits of the Library catalog analysis for research evaluation in Human and Social sciences. *Aib Studi*, 57(1), 7–22.
- Biagetti, M. T., Iacono, A., & Trombone, A. (2018). Is the Diffusion of Books in Library Holdings a Reliable Indicator in Research Assessment? In A. Bonaccorsi (Ed.), *The Evaluation of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities: Lessons from the Italian Experience* (pp. 321–343). Cham: Springer International Publishing. Retrieved August 18, 2021, from https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-68554-0_14
- FRBR in Open Vlacc: Theorie en invoerafspraken*. (2021). (p. 46). Retrieved from <http://openvlacc.cultuurconnect.be/regelgeving>
- Halevi, G., Nicolas, B., & Bar-Ilan, J. (2016). The complexity of measuring the impact of books. *Publishing Research Quarterly*, 32(3), 187–200.
- Hicks, D. (2005). The Four Literatures of Social Science. In H. F. Moed, W. Glänzel, & U. Schmoch (Eds.), *Handbook of Quantitative Science and Technology Research* (pp. 473–496). Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers. Retrieved February 11, 2021, from http://link.springer.com/10.1007/1-4020-2755-9_22
- Linmans, A. (2010). Why with bibliometrics the humanities does not need to be the weakest link: Indicators for research evaluation based on citations, library holdings, and productivity measures. *Scientometrics*, 83(2), 337–354.
- Macevičiūtė, E., & Borg, M. (2013). The current situation of e-books in academic and public libraries in Sweden. *Libellarium: Časopis za istraživanja u području informacijskih i srodnih znanosti*, 6(1–2), 13–28.
- Maleki, A. (2021). Why does library holding format really matter for book impact assessment?: Modelling the relationship between citations and altmetrics with print and electronic holdings. *Scientometrics*. Retrieved December 22, 2021, from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-04239-9>

Priem, J., Taraborelli, D., Groth, P., & Neylon, C. (2010, October 26). altmetrics: A manifesto – altmetrics.org. Retrieved April 7, 2022, from <http://altmetrics.org/manifesto/>

Sieber, J., & Gradmann, S. (2011). How to best assess monographs? An attempt to assess the impact of monographs using library infrastructure and Web 2.0 tools. *European Educational Research Quality Indicators*. Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Philosophische Fakultät I.

Torres-Salinas, D., Arroyo-Machado, W., & Thelwall, M. (2021). Exploring WorldCat identities as an altmetric information source: A library catalog analysis experiment in the field of Scientometrics. *Scientometrics*, 126(2), 1725–1743.

Torres-Salinas, D., & Moed, H. F. (2009). Library catalog analysis as a tool in studies of social sciences and humanities: An exploratory study of published book titles in economics. *Journal of informetrics*, 3(1), 9–26.

White, H. D., Boell, S. K., Yu, H., Davis, M., Wilson, C. S., & Cole, F. T. (2009). Libcitations: A measure for comparative assessment of book publications in the humanities and social sciences. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60(6), 1083–1096.

White, H. D., & Zuccala, A. A. (2018). Libcitations, worldcat, cultural impact, and fame. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 69(12), 1502–1512.

Zuccala, A., & Guns, R. (2013). Comparing Book Citations in Humanities Journals to Library Holdings: Scholarly Use Versus “Perceived Cultural Benefit” (rip). In J. Gorraiz, E. Schiebel, C. Gumpenberger, M. Horlesberger, & H. Moed (Eds.), *14th International Society of Scientometrics and Informetrics Conference (issi)* (pp. 353–360). Leuven: Int Soc Scientometrics & Informetrics-Issi. Retrieved August 4, 2021, from <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:000353961700028>

Zuccala, A., & White, H. D. (2015). Correlating Libcitations and Citations in the Humanities with WorldCat and Scopus Data. In A. A. Salah, Y. Tonta, A. a. A. Salah, C. Sugimoto, & U. Al (Eds.), *Proceedings of Issi 2015 Istanbul: 15th International Society of Scientometrics and Informetrics Conference* (pp. 305–316). Leuven: Int Soc Scientometrics & Informetrics-Issi. Retrieved August 4, 2021, from <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:000380499700046>